

Diagnosis and Definition of Performance Indicators for the Efficiency of the Steam Generation Process in a Biomass Boiler

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 29 November 2025	This article proposes a diagnostic approach to evaluate the efficiency of a biomass boiler steam generation process, specifically using sawdust as fuel, based on performance indicators. Four Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are addressed: thermal efficiency, particulate matter emissions (PME), technical availability, and unscheduled downtime. The measurement methods, critical process parameters, and applicable standards are detailed. Finally, performance indicators are calculated using the information obtained from the research carried out to define a baseline.
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I. INTRODUCTION

Steam generation from biomass represents a sustainable alternative with a lower carbon footprint compared to fossil fuels. The use of forest residues as a source of biomass for bioenergy generation is a potential alternative, as it produces a less polluting biofuel compared to fossil fuels (Ayala-Mendivil & Sandoval, 2018). Boilers that use sawdust as fuel are common in industries with wood by-products. However, to maximize their economic and environmental contribution, it is important to monitor and manage their performance actively. Failure to manage critical points in a process can lead to inefficient operations, high maintenance costs, and a suboptimal environmental impact (Tene et al., 2023). This study presents a systematic approach to addressing these challenges by defining a baseline based on performance indicators for the proper operation of biomass boilers.

The plant under study is dedicated to the manufacture of hand tools, most of which contain at least some wooden component, resulting in considerable waste from the manufacturing processes. This waste is used to fuel two biomass boilers. The steam generated by the boilers is used for the drying process, which consists of drying the wood in ovens to remove moisture in a controlled and rapid manner. The current steam demand for this process is 15,400 kg/h. The main boiler has a nominal capacity of 9,790 kg/h and is operating at 40% of its nominal capacity, producing 3,916

kg/h. The main problems encountered with the boiler are as follows:

- Limited fuel supply
- Poor fuel quality
- Lack of control in unscheduled shutdowns
- Lack of maintenance management

II. METHODS

Based on the problems and the current operation of the equipment, four KPIs are proposed and defined for the evaluation of boiler performance depending on the criteria.

A. Thermal efficiency

Represents the fraction of the energy contained in the fuel that is transferred to the steam generated. It is calculated using direct methods (energy balance between steam and fuel) or indirect methods (quantification of losses). Heat losses through the boiler body always occur by conduction, convection, and radiation (IDAE, 2007).

The efficiency of an installation can be obtained from the energy balance, considering the energy used and the energy delivered:

$$\eta = E_{\text{aprov}} / E_{\text{ent}} * 100\% \text{ Equation 1}$$

Where:

E_{aprov} : energy used by the working fluid.

E_{ent} : energy delivered to the system.

“Diagnosis and Definition of Performance Indicators for the Efficiency of the Steam Generation Process in a Biomass Boiler”

In this method, the energy supplied to the system is considered to be the energy released by the fuel (based on the lower heating value of the fuel) and the energy credits entering the system (sensible heat from the air, water, and fuel). The choice to use the lower heating value instead of the higher heating value is because, in the tested boilers, the water escapes through the chimney in a gaseous state without releasing its heat of condensation (Golato, 2008).

The direct method considers the steam generated, the temperature at the boiler inlet and outlet, as well as the fuel consumption and calorific value.

$$H=Q(H-h)/(q*GCV)*100\% \text{ Equation 2}$$

Where:

Q= Amount of steam generated

H= Enthalpy of steam

h= Enthalpy of water

q= Fuel consumption

GCV= Fuel calorific value

B. Technical availability

This is the percentage of total time the boiler is available to operate, excluding planned shutdowns. The variables to be measured are total operating time and unplanned downtime (duration and cause). To calculate availability, a historical record of failures, operating times, and repair times is required. MTBF and MTTR values are used for analysis based on average operating times and average repair times (Reyes, Linzan, & Ramos, 2021). The availability is defined by the following equation:

$$\text{Availability} = \frac{MTBF}{(MTBF + MTRR)} \text{ Equation 3}$$

Where:

MTBF: Mean time between failures

MTTR= Mean time between repairs

C. Unplanned downtime

These are unexpected interruptions in a process or equipment that halt production or service. They are caused by unforeseen failures, such as machinery breakdowns, operational errors, or inventory problems, and result in financial losses, delivery delays, and safety risks. This indicator is defined as equipment downtime and can have the following causes:

- Equipment failure: Mechanical, electrical, or component failures.
- Operational errors: Human errors or operator mistakes.
- Inadequate maintenance: Lack of preventive maintenance or a poor maintenance strategy.
- Management problems: Poor planning, lack of communication, or inventory problems.
- External factors: Supply chain disruptions or unforeseen events.

These stops must be recorded and reported by the operator. According to Carrasco (2016), the operator's

involvement is fundamental, as they are responsible for product quality and operational reliability.

D. Particulate matter emissions (PME)

This performance indicator helps us manage the percentage reduction of particulate matter (PM) and other pollutants relative to a baseline. PM is a visible mixture of small particles and gases in the air, generated by combustion. It is a significant pollutant in boilers that must be controlled. NOM-043-SEMARNAT-1993 establishes maximum permissible limits for the concentration of particulate matter (suspended particles), and NOM-085-SEMARNAT-2011 establishes limits for pollutants such as carbon monoxide (CO) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) from indirect heating combustion equipment that uses conventional fuels or their mixtures, to protect air quality. NOM-085-SEMARNAT-2011 does not apply in the following cases:

- Equipment with a nominal thermal capacity less than 530 MJ per hour (≈15 CC).
- Domestic heating and water heating equipment, gas turbines, auxiliary equipment, and backup equipment.
- Equipment that uses bioenergy. Bioenergy is a fuel obtained from biomass derived from organic matter from industrial activities (NOM-085-SEMARNAT-2011).

For biomass boilers, NOM-043-SEMARNAT-1993 applies, and NOM-085-SEMARNAT-2011 is taken only as a reference.

The maximum permissible limits for PM and main pollutants are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Maximum permissible emission levels for new equipment.

Month	Sawdust production (kg)
Jan	19,840
Feb	265,600
Mar	236,800
Apr	241,600
May	241,600
Jun	231,680
Jul	301,120
Aug	327,360
Sep	322,880
Oct	282,880
Grand Total	2,471,360

Source: NOM-085-SEMARNAT-2011..

III. RESULTS

The sawdust used for boiler operation comes from three different warehouses (A, B, and C), which are processed according to the daily production and operation of those

“Diagnosis and Definition of Performance Indicators for the Efficiency of the Steam Generation Process in a Biomass Boiler”

warehouses. Total production was estimated at 2,471,360 kg from January to October, as shown in Table 3 and Figure 1.

Table 3. Sawdust production in the period January-October 2025

Month	Sawdust production (kg)
Jan	19,840
Feb	265,600
Mar	236,800
Apr	241,600
May	241,600
Jun	231,680
Jul	301,120
Aug	327,360
Sep	322,880
Oct	282,880
Grand Total	2,471,360

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 1. Monthly sawdust production. Prepared by the author.

Table 4 and Figure 2 show the production by warehouse, indicating that warehouse B generates the most sawdust, with the other two serving only as support.

Table 4. Biomass production per warehouse.

Warehouse	Sawdust production (kg)
A	54,080
B	2,257,280
C	160,000
Total	2,471,360

Figure 2. Sawdust production per warehouse. Prepared by the author.

Production per shift is shown in Table 5 and Figure 3. There are four shifts, of which shifts 1, 2, and 3 generate a similar amount of sawdust. The fourth shift maintains a low level, as it is a shift where wood product production is low, and it is the shift where only orders that were not completed during the week are completed.

Table 5. Biomass production per warehouse.

Shift	Sawdust production(kg)
1	829,440
2	752,640
3	847,040
4	42,240
Total	2,471,360

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 3. Sawdust production per shift. Prepared by the author.

The plant has four boilers, two fueled by gas and two by biomass. The boiler to be analyzed is manufactured by HURST and is a water-tube boiler with a reciprocating grate for burning plant biomass (wood shavings, sawdust, wood chips), with the specifications shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Technical specifications of biomass boiler.

Parameter	100%	75%
Total consumption (kg/hr)	15,400	11,550
Theoretical installed capacity (kg/hr)	21,910	16,432
Actual installed capacity (kg/hr)	11,558	

Source: own elaboration.

This boiler is operating at 40% of its nominal capacity due to a limited fuel supply, generating 3,916 kg/hr of steam. The second biomass boiler produces 3,130 kg/hr operating at its nominal capacity, and the gas boilers produce 4,102 kg/hr each.

The average sawdust consumption is 535 kg/hr, which depends on the steam demand required for the kiln drying

“Diagnosis and Definition of Performance Indicators for the Efficiency of the Steam Generation Process in a Biomass Boiler”

process. According to the technical specifications, each kiln consumes 700 kg/hr of steam. With a total of 22 kilns operating in the plant, requiring a total of 15,400 kg/hr. Table 7 shows a summary of the consumption and capacities of the installed equipment in two possible scenarios, with 100% and 75% usage.

Table 7. Equipment consumption and capacity.

Specification	Value
Nominal capacity	5,060,000 kcal/h (600 B.H.P)
Max. saturated steam generated	9,790 kg/h
Total boiler efficiency	84% minimum

Source: own elaboration.

A. Thermal efficiency

The following considerations are taken into account for calculating thermal efficiency:

- The direct method is used, considering steam generation as known data obtained from the control panel
- The average value of fuel consumption per hour is taken
- Only dry wood is considered
- A lower heating value (PCI) of 4,539 kcal/kg is considered (Table 8)
- The water temperature at the boiler inlet is 70 °C
- The temperature of the saturated steam at the boiler outlet is 130 °C

Table 8. Average PCI and PCS values of the main fuels.

Fuel	Density	PCI				PCS
		kcal/kg	k Wh/kg	t e/kg	MJ /kg	
	kg/m ³					
Anthracite	875	8,19	9.5	8	34.	
Dry wood	-	4,53	5.2	4	19.	
Wet wood	-	3,44	4.0	3	14.	
						MJ/k g
						34.70
						-
						-

Source: IDAE, 2007.

Based on the above information, the required variables for calculating thermal efficiency are obtained, yielding a thermal efficiency of 89.74% (Table 9).

Table 9. Calculation of thermal efficiency.

Parameter	Variable	Value
Steam generated (kg/hr)	Q	3756
Enthalpy of vapor (KJ/kg) at 130 °C	H	2720.50
Enthalpy of water (KJ/kg) at 70 °C	h	292.98
Fuel consumption (kg/hr)	q	535
Calorific value of the fuel (kcal/kg)	GCV	4539
boiler efficiency %	η	89.74

Source: own elaboration.

B. Technical Availability

To determine equipment availability, two essential data points are required: the mean time between failures (MTBF) and the mean time to repair (MTTR). This data can be obtained using process management software such as SAP, specifically its "Plant Maintenance" module. Table 10 shows all boiler failures in 2024 and 2025, including the start date, start time, end date, and end time for each maintenance order, enabling calculation of the days between failures and repair times.

Table 10. Boiler failures in 2024 and 2025.

Equipment	Failure description	Order start date	Start time of order	End date of order	End time of order	Days between failures	Repairs hours
1-CAL-09	MC - INT. REPARACIÓN DE MOTOR 10HP #367	04/06/2024	10:30:00	04/06/2024	21:30:00	0	11
1-CAL-09	MS - CAMBIO DE SENSOR DE OXÍGENO	28/08/2024	12:00:00	28/08/2024	22:00:00	84	10
1-CAL-09	MP - 1-CAL-09 - MENSUAL	10/10/2024	22:30:00	11/10/2024	2:30:00	32	4
1-CAL-09	MS - INSTALACION DE MEDIDORES DE AGUA	29/10/2024	13:00:00	29/10/2024	17:00:00	19	2
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 6026711 TUBO CONDUIT DE PARO D	21/11/2024	17:00:00	21/11/2024	20:00:00	22	3
1-CAL-09	MONITOREO Y OPERACION DE EC	01.10.2024	6:00:00	01.11.2024	2:00:00		
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 5932830 CAMBIO DE TORNILLO DE	27/12/2024	9:30:00	27/12/2024	19:35:00	0	10
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 5932830 CORREGIR FUGA EN TUBER	27/12/2024	9:40:00	27/12/2024	19:45:00	0	10
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 6026711 FALTA TENSOR EN CADEN	27/12/2024	15:10:00	27/12/2024	17:10:00	0	2
1-CAL-09	MONITOREO Y OPERACION DE EC	01.05.2024	1:30:00	31.05.2024	23:59:00		
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 5946562 CALIBRAR SENSOR DE OX	28/12/2024	9:00:00	28/12/2024	11:00:00	1	2
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 5946562 REPARACION DE CAMISA D	28/12/2024	16:30:00	28/12/2024	18:40:00	0	2,16
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 6039748 TUBO CONDUIT DE PARO D	28/12/2024	8:20:00	28/12/2024	18:25:00	0	10
1-CAL-09	MS - REVISAR SENSOR DE AGUA	30/03/2025	11:00:00	30/03/2025	12:00:00	92	1
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 6098821 CAMBIO DE SENSOR DE TE	09/04/2025	10:24:22	09/04/2025	12:00:00	39	1,5
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 6098821 CAMBIO DE SENOSR DE ME	16/05/2025	6:00:03	16/05/2025	10:00:00	37	4
1-CAL-09	MP - 1-CAL-09 - MENSUAL		0:00:00		0:00:00		
1-CAL-09	MS-FABRICACION DE TOLVA CAL HURTS	05/06/2025	12:10:00	30/06/2025	14:00:00	19	1,84
1-CAL-09	Sensores Metering	20/06/2025	11:00:00	20/06/2025	11:30:00	15	0,5
1-CAL-09	MC - 6146980 CAMBIO DE SENSORES METERING	24/06/2025	12:09:28	24/06/2025	11:10:00	4	1
1-CAL-09	MS-INSTALACION DE TOLVA CAL HURTS	01/07/2025	17:30:00	17/07/2025	13:30:00	7	40
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 6098821 CAMBIO DE SENSOR DE OX	10/07/2025	9:00:00	10/07/2025	10:30:00	9	1,5
1-CAL-09	MPD 1-CAL-09 OTT 293	03.07.2025	14:49:24	07.07.2025	0:00:00		
1-CAL-09	MS-FABRICACION DE TOLVA CAL HURTS	17/07/2025	18:00:00	18/07/2025	16:00:00	7	22
1-CAL-09	Falla en sensores	25/07/2025	8:00:00	25/07/2025	12:00:00	12	4
1-CAL-09	Falla en PLC	25/07/2025	9:29:48	25/07/2025	12:00:00	0	1,5
1-CAL-09	CAMBIO DE SENSOR DE METERING JAM DAÑADO (RESERVA)	01/08/2025	14:00:00	01/08/2025	15:30:00	6	1,5
1-CAL-09	CVOXPVO - 6168268 ACTUAREPARACION EN CHA	11/08/2025	11:00:00	12/08/2025	1:00:00	10	2
1-CAL-09	CVOXRL - 6205081 CAMBIO DE ACEITE EN DEP	17/10/2025	12:00:00	17/10/2025	14:00:00	6	2
						17,54	6,02

Source: own elaboration.

C. Unplanned downtime

Unplanned downtime must be recorded and managed to identify and mitigate its potential causes. This is done through a logbook, either physical or digital, recording the date, reason for the downtime, and the equipment downtime. Table 11 and Figure 6 show the unscheduled downtime for the last few months, totaling 79 hours.

Table 11. Downtime per month.

Month	Downtime (hrs)
Apr	19
May	46.5
Jul	10
Aug	3.5
Total	79

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 6. Time off per month. Source: Prepared by the author.

The main incidents (Table 12) are due to power outages and the repair of scrapers (discharge mechanism). Power outages depend on an external supplier, and although they cannot be controlled, a response protocol can be developed for when this problem occurs.

Table 12. Boiler incidents.

Incidents	Time stoppage (hrs)	% Accumulated
CFE power outage strike	36	22%
Repair of squeegees	14.5	48%
The boiler shut down due to a lack of sawdust to feed	13	70%
Safety stops are not released for start-up	4	74%
Stoppage due to filter change	3.5	83%
Out of service due to a blockage in the ducts	3	87%
The boiler is out of service for not meeting conditions safe food	3	96%
Stoppage for area cleaning	2	100%
Total	79	

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 7. Incidents in biomass boiler. Source: Prepared by the author.

Table 13 shows that the third shift is where the greatest impact of downtime occurs, with 38.5 hours. This is due to various factors, such as a lack of personnel and supervision during this shift.

Table 13. Boiler incidents.

Shift	Downtime (hrs)
1	19
2	21.5
3	38.5
Total	79

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 8. Incidents in biomass boiler per shift. Source: Prepared by the author.

D. Environmental performance

To measure the energy performance of a steam boiler, pollutant emissions such as total suspended particles, carbon monoxide, and nitrogen oxides are measured. If the equipment and trained personnel to perform these measurements are unavailable, it is necessary to hire an external provider.

Table 14 shows the parameters, methods, and standards used by Servicios de Consultoría y Verificación Ambiental, SA de CV (SECOVAM).

Table 14. Identification of equipment, evaluation dates, evaluation method, and standards with which it is compared.

No.	Control number	Equipment identification and evaluation date	Evaluated parameters	Evaluation method	Official Mexican standard that establishes the maximum permissible limits
1	144PPF25-07	PIC Boiler No. 9 600 CC (June 23, 2025)	Partículas suspendidas totales	NMX-AA-009-1993-SCFI NMX-AA-010-SCFI-2001	NOM-043-SEMARNAT-1993
2	144PPF25-09	PIC Boiler No. 7 (June 23, 2025)		Monóxido de carbono Óxidos de nitrógeno	

Source: SECOVAM, 2025.

The results of the evaluation carried out on the two biomass boilers are shown in Table 15. For the concentration of suspended particles, the comparison with the standard was made using the average of both runs.

Table 15. Results of total suspended particles assessment.

No.	Equipment	Parameter	Particle concentration, referred to STP and dry base (mg/m ³ N)	LMPE established in NOM-043-SEMARNAT-1993 (mg/m ³ N)	Conclusion
1	PIC Boiler No. 9 600 CC	Partículas suspendidas totales	120.414	810.080	OK
2	PIC Boiler No. 7		67.142	588.535	OK

Source: SECOVAM, 2025.

CO and NO_x measurements are evaluated for reference purposes only, as the equipment uses non-conventional fuel (Table 16).

Table 16. Results of the evaluation of CO and NO_x assessment in biomass boilers.

No.	Equipment	Parameter	Concentration of the pollutant determined for the chimney (ppmV)	Concentration refers to 5% O ₂ and dry base (ppmV)	LMPE established in NOM-085-SEMARNAT-2011 (ppmV)	Conclusion
1	PIC Boiler No. 9 600 CC	CO	324.474	874.431	Not applicable	Not applicable
		NO _x	35.012	94.354	Not applicable	Not applicable
2	PIC Boiler No. 7	CO	231.147	622.923	Not applicable	Not applicable
		NO _x	6.655	17.934	Not applicable	Not applicable

Source: SECOVAM, 2025.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This diagnostic guide calculating and manages KPIs in sawdust-fired biomass boilers. By implementing this diagnosis, plants can:

1. Establish a robust baseline: Quantify current performance for future comparisons.
2. Identify areas for improvement: Through continuous deviation analysis and root cause analysis.
3. Ensure regulatory compliance: Guarantee operation within emission and safety limits.

The benchmark for generating improvements is based on the constant comparison of calculated KPIs with the objectives predefined by management. Any negative deviation triggers the process and implementation of corrective and preventive actions, ensuring continuous progress toward operational excellence and sustainability.

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